

Evaluation of Restoration Interventions in the Ancient Theater of Ephesus in Terms of National and International Conservation Principles

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Abstract

Theaters, which can be integrated into contemporary life without altering their original construction purposes, are cultural heritages of documentary nature. International platforms established rules for their use for events and conservation of cultural traces they possess. The preservation and restoration efforts in theaters, aimed at bringing them back into modern life, have evolved over time, reflecting shifts in techniques and approaches from past to present. The study aims to emphasize why and how changing restoration techniques have been used in the theaters' integration into contemporary life and to evaluate restoration works conducted over the years on these monuments in the context of national and international conservation legislation. The scope was determined as the Ancient Theater of Ephesus, where the first restoration works began with the Ephesus Festival organized in 1968, and continued subsequently for tourism-related events. A literature review covering the national and international statutes and laws was conducted to examine the changing restoration works over time, and findings from on-site observations were conveyed through plans and photographs.

Keywords: Contemporary use, the ancient theater of Ephesus, conservation and restoration.

Efes Antik Tiyatrosu'ndaki Restorasyon Müdahalelerinin Ulusal ve Uluslararası Koruma İlkeleri Bağlamında Değerlendirilmesi

Öz

Yapılış amacı değiştirilmeden çağdaş yaşama katılabilen tiyatrolar, taşıdıkları kültürel izlerle belgesel nitelikteki miraslardır. Tiyatroların etkinlikler için kullanımı ve taşıdıkları kültürel izlerin korunması için uluslararası platformlarda altı çizili kurallar belirlenmiştir. Çalışmanın amacı, antik alanlarda zaman içerisinde değişen restorasyon tekniklerinin tiyatroların çağdaş yaşama katılma süreçlerinde nedenli ve nasıl ele alındığını vurgulamaktır. Çalışmanın hedefi ise bu anıt eserlerde yıllara sâri yapılan restorasyon çalışmalarının ulusal ve uluslararası koruma mevzuatları bağlamında değerlendirilmesidir. Çalışmanın kapsamı, 1968'de düzenlenen Efes Festivali ile birlikte ilk restorasyon çalışmaları yapılan, sonraki yıllarda turizm amaçlı etkinlikler için tekrar restorasyon çalışmaları sürdürülen Efes Antik Tiyatro'su olarak belirlenmiştir. Zamanla değişen restorasyon çalışmalarını incelemek amacıyla ulusal ve uluslararası alanlardaki tüzükleri ve yasaları kapsayan literatür araştırması yapılmış, yerinde yapılan gözlemlerle edinilen bulgular planlar ve fotoğraflar üzerinden aktarılmıştır.

Anahtar kelimeler: Çağdaş kullanım, Efes Antik Tiyatro, koruma ve onarım, restorasyon.

Citation: Yılmaz, B. & Suri, L. (2024). Evaluation of restoration interventions in the Ancient Theater of Ephesus in terms of national and international conservation principles. *Journal of Protected Areas Research*, 3 (2), 141-154.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14544357>

1. Introduction

As stated in the Charter on the Use of Ancient Places of Performance, issued as a result of the Conference of the Council of Europe held in Verona, theaters are among the very few monuments that can still serve their original purposes under particular circumstances. Together with the cultural traces they possess, they are living cultural heritages of artistic and documentary nature, covering a broad range of processes from the periods when they were built to the restorations they underwent and the alternative uses they served over time (Council of Europe [COE], 1997). While religious rituals, sacred ceremonies and parades were among the primary purposes of use of these heritages until today, it is seen that they began to serve social purposes over time due to changing socio-cultural factors (Çorbacı, 2007). The conservation and restoration works, carried out in the theaters that have been desired to be reintegrated into contemporary life, have continued from the past to the present with changing techniques and approaches.

In this study, the Ancient Theater of Ephesus was examined to compare the changes in conservation and restoration techniques that began seventeen years after its public opening for its use as an event venue and have continued over the years since then. The fact that the reflection of conservation and restoration works carried out in the theater for the same purpose in different periods on the national and international legislation are accessible, and that the continuity of the concept of conservation can be observed despite changing techniques played an important role in the selection of the theater, integrated into contemporary life as an event venue, as the subject of the study.

Within the scope of the study, the first comprehensive conservation and restoration works started in the Ephesus Archeological Site, which was opened in 1951, with the Ephesus Festival organized in 1968 and turned into an international event, and the more recent conservation and restoration works, carried out in 2018-2021 and completed with another event, were examined.

1.1. Historical Background of the Ancient City of Ephesus

Situated in the present-day Selçuk District, 79 km south of İzmir province and established in the Küçük Menderes delta, the Ancient City of Ephesus has been home to many different civilizations throughout the ages. Designated as a world heritage site in 2015, the first foundation of the city dates back to 7000 BC. The settlement and harbor area of the city has changed over historical processes due to historical events and geographical conditions (Türkoğlu, 2000). In the area covering approximately 585 hectares, traces of urbanization, architectural structures and layers of beliefs forming a wide spectrum from the Neolithic period to the Republican period are seen together (Table 1).

Table 1. Historical periods of Ephesus (Selçuk Municipality, 2022)

Historical Period	Settlement Area
Neolithic, Chalcolithic and Early Bronze Age	Çukuriçi Höyük ('Çukuriçi Mound')
Bronze Age and Iron Age	Ayasuluk Hill and Surroundings of the Temple of Artemis
Archaic and Classical Periods	Ayasuluk Hill, Artemis, Mt Pion (Panayır)
Hellenistic Period	Ephesus, 4 th century BC –31 BC
Roman Period	Ephesus, 31 BC –293 AD
Byzantine Period	Ephesus and Ayasuluk, 293 AD – 13 th century
Principality Period	Ayasuluk, 1304 – 1426
Ottoman Period	Ayasuluk, 1426 – 1923
Republican Period	Selçuk

Ephesus World Heritage Site can be expressed in four parts as important historical processes. Çukuriçi Höyük, the earliest Neolithic and Bronze Age settlement, was discovered during excavations in 1995. It is believed that the settlement here was abandoned in the early 3rd century BC with its destruction. It is mentioned in written sources that the settlement shifted to Ayasuluk region as of the mid-Bronze Age. Hittite records refer to the city of Apasa, the main settlement of the land of Arwaza, located in

the Ayasuluk region, addressing to the late 2000 BCE. It is thought that the name "Apasas" corresponds to "Ephesus" in Greek (Selcuk Municipality, 2022).

Greek culture increased in the ancient city of Ephesus, being dated back to 1000 BC.. The Temple of Artemis, one of the seven wonders of world today, is dated as a construction of this period (Selcuk Municipality, 2022). Known as the house of gods, the temple is the most important sacred place of the settlement. During this period, there was a harbor located to the north of the temple, near Ayasuluk Hill. Like many wars created turning points in history, the Persian and Spartan war continued until the siege by Alexander the Great. After Alexander's death in 300 BC, one of his generals, the Macedonian Commander Lysimachus founded Ephesus in its present location. Although the Ephesians were reluctant to leave their old settlement, the people were forced to settle in the Arsinoe region, named after the commander's wife. During this period, a new harbor and defensive walls were built in the city, which was established between Mt Pion and Mt Koressos. The city was designed in a grid plan (Ladstatter et al., 2016).

Few remains from the Hellenistic period survived in the city until today. The most magnificent structure belonging to this period is the Great Theater, exhibiting influences of the Hellenistic period, and the fountain to its west. After the death of the Macedonian commander, the city started to be called Ephesus again. After Ephesus became part of the Roman Empire in 133 BC, the city highly developed as the new capital of Anatolia (Selcuk Municipality, 2022).

The Ancient City of Ephesus experienced the period when important architectural structures came into prominence in the 2nd century. Many magnificent buildings were constructed thanks to the donations and supports of the leading families of the city. The Temples of Domitian and Hadrian, and the Library of Celsus are the notable buildings of this period. One of the turning points in the city was the closure of the Temple of Artemis in 381 and its use as a quarry with the spread of Christianity. Similarly, many similar buildings in the city were abandoned and churches were constructed. However, by the 9th century, the military and political power of Samos and Smyrna provinces increased, leading Ephesus to lose its importance, and the city was reconstructed around the old harbor area. Thus, from the 10th century onwards, urban textures emerged around Ayasuluk Hill (Selcuk Municipality, 2022).

With the Battle of Maznikert in 1071, Anatolian Turkish Principalities began to dominate the region. Aydinid dynasty (the Principality of Aydın) ruled the region, and the Ottoman Empire era started with the end of the period of principalities. From the late 17th century until the early 19th century, Selçuk suffered from epidemic diseases and as a result, the population density declined significantly and the city lost its vitality in social and economic terms. However, with the increase in the investment activities of the Ottoman Empire in the 19th century, the industrial sector developed in the city and commercial trade and social life started to revive. The construction of the İzmir-Aydın railway, the first railway in Anatolia, started in 1858. Although it reached Selçuk in 1862, it was completed in eight years after a challenging construction process, reaching its final destination, Aydın, in 1866 (Cobb, 2023).

Another aspect that makes the Ephesus cultural heritage site important is the belief in Christianity that after her death, the Virgin Mary ascends to heaven on August 15 each year (Assumption/Dormition). With this belief, Christians visit the church of the Virgin Mary on Mt Koressos every year. Visits for this purpose make Ephesus one of the key sites for religious tourism.

1.2. The Great Theater

Architect John Turtle Wood, who came to the city in 1863 to study the Temple of Artemis, received a decree from the Ottoman Government with the support of the British Museum authorities and started the first excavations in the area. He continued his excavation works until 1874 in the important structures in the city to provide financial support for his quest to find the Temple of Artemis (Ürüm, 2014). The most important of these significant monuments is the Great Theater of Ephesus. Following the works in 1800s, various excavations and archaeological studies have been conducted in the area by the Austrian Archaeological Institute, which still continue today.

With a capacity of 24,000 people, the Ancient Theater of Ephesus is one of the focal points of the city center, being the largest and most magnificent theater built by human in Anatolia. The construction of

the theater, part of which leans against the slope of Mt Pion and which is located at the intersection of Harbor (Arcadian) Street and Marble Road, commenced in the Hellenistic Period and the theater was expanded during the reign of Emperor Claudius between 41-54 AD during Roman Imperial Period. It was completed during the reign of Emperor Trajan between 97-117 AD (Anadolu, 2001).

The theater lost its Hellenistic characteristic in the Roman Period, enlarged with periodic interventions and its shape was constantly changed. Today, it is a mass slightly larger than a semicircle with a diameter of approximately 150 meters. The architectural layout of the structure in general consists of the stage building, caveas (seating area) and orchestra pit (Figure 1).

Figure 1. General view of the theater after conservation and restoration works carried out in 2018-2021 (Republic of Türkiye Ministry of Culture and Tourism, 2021)

The stage building originally had three stories, but only the basement and some remnants from upper-story survive today. The building is approximately 43 meters wide and 23 meters deep. The basement of the stage building comprises of 8 rooms aligned along an east-west axis, a corridor connecting these rooms and 4 support rows carrying the Roman Period stage. All facing stones of the building with closed arched entrances (parodoi) on the ground floor have been lost. In addition, the remains of the walls in the building, which was incorporated into the city walls during the Byzantine Period can be still seen.

The caveas of the theater, divided into three sections by two diazomata (walkways between seats), containing a total of 65 rows, the highest of which is 30 m above the orchestra floor, are visible even from a great distance when approaching from Kuşadası towards Selçuk. The first tier of seating areas is reached from the south by a sloping ramp, the other parts are reached from the north and again the south by vaulted passageways with stairs in the Analemmata (supporting walls). The auditorium, resembling a giant half funnel, has an incline of approximately 33 degrees. The orchestra pit, which is larger than a semicircle, and the surrounding active water channel, where we can observe traces of Hellenistic and Roman Period together, have survived to the present day in a well-preserved structural

2. Material and Method

In the article, the conservation status of the building, the interventions made for the problems in building stones, consideration of the aesthetic compatibility of the works and methods of indication within the context of conservation legislation are discussed. The interventions carried out in the theater over various periods were examined in more detail with the visual analysis technique and

literature review, and the conservation and restoration works conducted at different times with the same purpose were compared.

3. Findings and Discussion

The Ancient Theater of Ephesus is one of the rare cultural heritage sites included in the UNESCO World Heritage List among the theaters that can serve their original purpose by involving into contemporary life, albeit intermittently, from the 60s to the present day. The building shows construction phases from different periods, and these phases differ in terms of material, technique and design. In this context, although the comprehensive conservation and restoration works carried out in the monument, having the characteristic of a historical document, which is in a very good condition in terms of observability, serve the same purpose, they differ from each other in terms of approach, type of material used and stylistic aspects. The latest conservation and restoration works in the theater should serve as a model for ensuring that cultural heritages which are integrated into contemporary life are simultaneously carried to the future sturdily.

3.1. Comprehensive Conservation and Restoration Works in the Theater

Integration of archeological monuments into contemporary life by organizing cultural events such as exhibitions, concerts, operas and theaters there helps to make the site widely known, allows the local people to acquire awareness while familiarizing with art and culture and to actively participate in the conservation of the monuments and also provides funds for conservation works (Ahunbay, 2010). In the recent years, important monuments in the Ancient City of Ephesus such as the Bouleuterion, the Great Theater, Library of Celsus, Atrium Thermarum and Arcadian Street have been integrated into contemporary life by cultural activity organizations.

In the archeological site, which was officially opened to visit in 1951, the Ephesus Festival was organized in 1962 with the participation of local community and under the organization of the local administration; and thus, the site began to be used as a festival venue (Aktüre, 2012). With the festival, excavation works and first comprehensive restoration efforts were carried out by the museum directorate in the 1960s and 70s to use the ancient theater as an active event venue. During these works, some parts of the caveas of the theater were repaired with original materials while some of the parts were completed using concrete materials (Hofbauer et al., 2017). In addition to the restoration works at caveas, the restorations started on the orchestra floor, south analemma wall and the Hellenistic Fountain of the theater and continued over time (Türkoğlu, 2000). Atalay, 1973) highlighted the extent of these interventions in the Annual of the Ruins and Museum of Ephesus, stating, "After the completion of the restoration of the Great Theater of Ephesus, its grandeur in ancient times reappeared and it became the only large structure visible when looking towards Ephesus from the shores of the city of Claros" (s.51).

By the early 90s, the impact of increasing modern use, as well as frequent winds in Ephesus, cold and rainy winter, hot and humid climatic conditions, especially the rapid drying in July and August, affected the ancient structure negatively (Hofbauer et al., 2017). The structure, showing signs of wear and tear, became unsafe for visitors. To reduce the impact of severe earthquakes on the large building blocks in the theater and ensure safety of the building and its construction elements, a joint damage assessment was conducted by the competent Turkish authorities in collaboration with the Austrian excavation site director St. Karwiese and Turkish architect İ. Ataç. Urgent measures to strengthen the theater were determined (Altıntaş, 2008). These efforts focused on the western sections, including the external walls of the auditorium. Within this context, additional excavation works were also carried out in the corridors providing access to the lower and middle diazomata (Hofbauer et al., 2017).

In 2012, during the tenure of Ertuğrul Günay, Minister of Culture and Tourism, the ancient theater served its original purpose once again and hosted the Berlin Philharmonic Orchestra. Before this cultural event, conservation and restoration works had been carried out for approximately four years starting in 2008 by the excavation site directorate and under the supervision of Ephesus Museum (Ladstatter, 2012).

The focus of these works was mainly on the reinforcement and strengthening of the monument. However, numerous previous conservation interventions, which were harmful to the building and partially impossible to be removed, complicated the works. Since the Summa Cavea section was closed to visit, only cleaning works were conducted there, and diazoma and entrance areas of the building were reinforced for directing the visitor circulation safely. In addition, reinforcement works were also carried out at the orchestra floor, the surrounding channel and orchestra stairs. Another focus of the works was the South Analemma wall in the southern part of the theater, which had been significantly affected by the earthquakes in the past and was statically unstable (Ladstatter, 2016).

Ladstatter (2016), the excavation site director at the time, stated the works conducted at that section in the article "Conservation Strategies in the Archeological Sites of Ephesus" as follows:

"The works at the South Analemma, which had lost its stability due to severe earthquake damage, were particularly challenging. It was necessary to install a steel construction to prevent a previously detached vault block from falling, to keep it in place and secure the chambers in the structure below. The modular steel structure was fully reversible and matches the protective roof of the Terrace House 2 visually. To reinforce the statically dangerous sections of the facade and cavea, telescopic poles that could be removed when desired were used. Controlled visitor access was provided by the consolidation of the entrances both in the orchestra and in the first diazoma. In the fall of 2012, the Great Theater of Ephesus was opened for cultural events under strict monument conservation rules, and the visitor capacity was restricted to 2,200 visitors" (p. 546).

Maintenance and restoration works continued in the theater over the years. The density of events was reduced and the monument was completely closed for performances and concerts in 2018. The second comprehensive conservation and restoration work was started. When this work was completed, the theater reopened its doors for performances in 2021, hosting three international events within the festival (Erbalaban Yilmaz, 2021). The conservation and restoration works, which lasted for three years, were carried out under the supervision of the relevant ministry control office by a team consisting of the project owner, the Austrian Excavation Site Directorate, the Ephesus Museum Directorate, the science committee and the contractor. The northern parodos walls of the theater, a part of the northern section of caveas, the orchestra pit and the stage building were the main focuses within the scope of the works. During the works conducted, the building's cultural heritage status of documentary nature was approached sensitively, together with the late-period additions which were preserved in some parts. Reinforcement and strengthening works in the theater, which was located on the bedrock (conglomerate) in the south, but on vaults in the north, were carried out primarily at the northern section. The Media Cavea Wall, which was statically unstable and a late-period intervention, was dismantled and reconstructed by using materials and construction techniques in harmony with the original. Unqualified repairs were removed from the cavea sections, which had been reconstructed with concrete completions and repaired with cement mortars in 70s, and stone completions were performed following approach principles appropriate to the existing texture.

The northern parodos walls at the entrance of the theater on Harbor Street axis, which feature early examples of vandalism, having material losses and cracks in the building stones, were reinforced and completed with stone materials appropriate to the original. Conservation works were performed on the stage building, which has empty joints, micro-cracks in the building stones, structural cracks in the northern entrance lintel and the late-period concrete leveling floor covering. The late-period floor covering, which was partially reconstructed with reinforced concrete material, in the orchestra area, the center for events, was removed. The original floor paving stones, of which a very small part has been preserved to the present day, were protected and floor covering was constructed with stone slabs. Furthermore, in the orchestra area, imitation completions were made using hydraulic-lime-based mortar at the section between the profiled ground circle and orchestra retaining wall. Conservation works were carried out on the ous sectile remains that have survived to the present day in some sections.

3.2. Comparative Evaluation of the Works

3.2.1. Interventions in the cavea sections

The restorations dated to the 70s in the cavea sections exhibit rubble stone masonry and reinforced concrete completions with different textures and cement mortar repairs. In addition, the stairs, which are among the vertical circulation elements providing access to the cavea sections, were reconstructed in multi-part by use of rubble stone and cement mortar in some sections, while in other sections they were entirely rebuilt with monolithic concrete. When the northern cavea sections of the auditorium were examined, it was observed that in the Ima Cavea (First Cavea) section, the large gaps behind the thin pitch-faced stones were filled with cement mortar; in the Media Cavea (Second Cavea) section, the large gaps behind the pitch-faced stones were also mainly filled with cement mortar; in the Summa Cavea (Third Cavea) section, different rubble stone masonry and entirely reinforced concrete completions were performed in places where the density of pitch-faced stones was very low or non-existent (Figure 2).

Figure 2.a.Repairs with cement-based mortar and concrete completions made in the 70s (Republic of Türkiye Ministry of Culture and Tourism, 2021), .b.The difference in texture of the completions with hydraulic-lime-based mortar and stones carried out during works between 2019-2021 and the parts with cement repairs made in the 70s (Yılmaz, 2019-2021)

In the latest restoration works carried out in the theater, the interventions in the cavea were categorized under three main titles, the first of which is rubble stone completion, the second is completion with hydraulic-lime-based mortar and the third is rubble stone completion with pitch-faced stones. If the common principles of the restoration works, which are seen together with all the interventions in the cross-section below, are discussed, it can be said that the gap behind the existing pitch-faced stone in the cavea served as a guide. While rubble stone completions were made where the gaps were approximately 30-40 cm, completions were made with hydraulic-lime-based mortar in places where the gaps behind the existing pitch-facing stones were less than 7-8 cm deep. In places where the original pitch-facing stones were entirely missing, completions were made with new pitch-facing stones, maintaining a minimum 40 cm and a maximum 70 cm width in the front part of the cavea seating units. The back parts of the placed pitch-facing stones were filled with new rubble stones, matching the color of the existing stones (Figure 3).

Figure 3. a. Detailed cross section of the cavea completions made between 2018-2021 (Republic of Türkiye Ministry of Culture and Tourism, 2021), b. Samples of cavea completions made between 2018-2021 (Yılmaz, 2019-2021)

The cement inserts in the stairs were also removed during the cavea works. Instead of monolithic concrete steps, which were placed in a way to divide the height of each cavea seating unit in two steps, new stars made of stone material were built by preserving the end axes and heights of the cavea seating units. The stone stairsteps were formed using monolithic pitch-facing stones for smaller step parts and two pieces of pitch-facing stones for the larger steps below (Figure 4).

Figure 4. a. Concrete steps with cement repairs made in the 70s (Republic of Türkiye Ministry of Culture and Tourism, 2021), b. Steps formed with freestones during the works between 2018-2021 (Yılmaz, 2019-2021)

3.2.2. Interventions in the M4 Cavea Wall

The western parodos entrance, starting at the end of Harbor Street, leads visitors to the diazoma that divides the Media and Ima Cavea through a vaulted passage with rising stairs in the Roman Period Theater. However, some parts of the northern caveas, constructed on vaults, have not survived to the present day due to the impact of the major earthquake in the past. In the late period restorations, the substructure of the M4 Cavea was constructed with a sequential layering technique using rubble stones of different sizes with cement mortar in order to function as a retaining wall. Signs of static weakening and out-of-plane deformations were observed on this wall, which was a later-period addition (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Reinforcement works carried out on the M4 Cavea substructure in the 70s. (Republic of Türkiye Ministry of Culture and Tourism, 2021)

Within the scope of the latest conservation and restoration works in the theater, the retaining wall was constructed in two stages to provide sufficient static support to the caveas and to ensure the continuity of the appearance of cavea substructure. In the first stage, a wall where the cavea seating units leaned was constructed with large-sized pitch-facing stones using hydraulic-lime-based mortar, to serve as a retaining wall. In the second stage, a wall with a sloped and indented front face was constructed in front of the pitch-facing stone wall, using small-sized rubble stones based on the restitutive information and referring to the cavea substructure rubble stone masonry. Thus, reinforcement was provided with a concealed retaining wall, indirectly suggesting the presence of the cavea sections that are no longer visible when visited today (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Reinforcement works between 2018-2021 (Republic of Türkiye Ministry of Culture and Tourism, 2021)

3.2.3. Interventions in the Parodos Walls

Parodos walls run along the Harbor Street and define the western entrance at the end of the street. It is one of the entrances frequently used in contemporary events. The walls border both sides of the stairs leading to the Media Cavea Diazoma. The walls, which still show examples of the first vandalism, were severely affected by past major earthquakes and statically weakened. Continuous maintenance and repair works were conducted in the past by the responsible authorized institutions, and the parts with deep openings and large-scale material losses posing risks were supported with metal poles for reinforcement.

Comprehensive interventions were carried out in the recent works to address the structural problems and building material problems of the parodos walls. The necessary conservation works were performed by reinforcing the cracks, gaps and broken pieces on the building blocks. In addition, the empty joints within the inner masonry were renewed, and medium-sized gaps were completed with rubble stones and mortar to prevent rainwater destruction. The free soil on top of both sections was capped so that the inner masonry was protected from rainwater destruction. In the inner masonry and external surface, where large material losses were seen, partial stone completion was carried out,

where needed, using textures and materials matching the original. In this way, the structure's load-bearing system was restored and the original masonry technique of the wall was made observable through the partial stone completions on the external surface (Figure 7).

Figure 7. a. Sample of the reinforcement works on the Parodos walls, stones supported with metal poles (Yılmaz, 2019-2021). b. Partial stone completion during reinforcement and strengthening works between 2018-2021 (Yılmaz, 2019-2021). c. Wall stones supported with metal poles (Yılmaz, 2019-2021). d. Partial stone completion during reinforcement works between 2018-2021 (Yılmaz, 2019-2021)

3.2.4. Interventions in the Orchestra Pit

Layers from ancient periods can be observed in the present orchestra of the theater. Structurally, the orchestra of the Hellenistic period was expanded and elevated during the Roman Empire period and took its present form. The Roman orchestra area consists of seven parts between the cavea and stage building, which can be named as follows: orchestra retaining (support) wall, epicycle gap, profiled ground circle, water channel, floor, stage border (logeion - proskenion) and stairs.

The stage building or orchestra areas are the units where circulation is highly active in terms of functional use in the ancient theaters that are integrated into contemporary life today. Most parts of the original marble floor covering of the theater, hosting festivals for many years, has been lost, with only a small part preserved until today (Figure 8).

Figure 8. Original orchestra floor paving stones within the red frame (Republic of Türkiye Ministry of Culture and Tourism, 2021)

In the late period interventions made in order to prepare the orchestra for performances and events, the lost parts of the floor covering were partially completed with marble pieces of varying sized and colors, and mostly with concrete imitation coverings in different sizes in an alternating pattern. In these completions, the original flooring elevation was taken as a reference, but the concern of distinguishing between the original and the completed parts was not reflected in the works (Figure 9). In addition, the parts of the concrete wall were formed with repairs made using cement-based mortars and in-situ marble stones in some places in the approximately 1.70 meter high and 60-meter-long boundary retaining support wall of the orchestra pit.

Figure 9. Concrete imitation floor coverings made in the 70s (Republic of Türkiye Ministry of Culture and Tourism, 2021)

In the last restoration works carried out in the orchestra, the concrete imitations were removed and horizontal axis completed were made in the floor covering with light gray-white, honed natural stone slabs. The areas with original marble paving stones preserved until today were separated from the present-day completions by forming a boundary with hydraulic-lime-based contour mortar. Additionally, in the completion based on the original Roman Orchestra leveling, reference was made to the Roman Orchestra elevated after the Hellenistic Period and the texture of the orchestra substructure before floor covering. The Hellenistic Channel, which runs around the orchestra and still actively drains rainwater from south to north, was not covered as it was during the Roman Period, allowing visitors to explore both ancient periods (Figure 10).

Figure 10. a. The orchestra after the completion of works between 2018-2021 (Yılmaz, 2021). b. Border mortar around the original paving stones (Yılmaz, 2019-2021)

In addition, as part of these works, only the joining parts of the in-situ marble stones and the imitation concrete stone plaster on the orchestra retaining wall were separated, bounded with hydraulic-lime-based mortar. Thus, the salinization effect of the cement was separated from the marble stones, while concrete-completed wall was preserved as a period restoration.

As a result, the effect of the cement's salting was kept apart from the marble stones, but the wall's completed concrete structure was kept intact as a historical restoration. The soil-covered outer circle gap served as one of the circulation areas in the past. To maintain flexibility and reversibility while incorporating ergonomics into modern usage, imitation flooring was completed using hydraulic lime-based mortar and the circle's required radial form (Figure 11).

Figure 11. a. Restoration intervention on the orchestra retaining wall in the 70s (Republic of Türkiye Ministry of Culture and Tourism, 2021). b. The retaining wall and epicycle gap imitation with mortar after the works between 2018-2021 (Yılmaz, 2019-2021)

4. Conclusion and Recommendations

Throughout the history, there has been a desire to integrate the ancient buildings into contemporary life by organizing festivals, performances and various events at ancient sites. The underlying factors behind this desire are the wish to recognize or increase the recognition of these monuments, along with educating, teaching and raising awareness while human factors are in close interaction with culture and art. On the other hand, it should be noted that ancient monuments are extremely sensitive structures despite being educational and enlightening. Should a list of sensitivities be made, theaters would rank at top of this list, having a high risk of wear and tear. The increasing number of visitors especially during summer months and the frequency of the concerts and events with the participation of large crowds can be damaging particularly if measures are not taken. The Ancient Theater of Ephesus, which shows signs of wear and tear due to the effects of adverse natural events and the

increasing modern use since the date it hosted festivals until the 90s, can serve as an example of a site turning into an unsafe place for its guests to visit.

On the other hand, conservation and restoration works carried out in theaters, which are living historical documents of cultural, artistic and periodical changes, play a major role in their sound transmission to future generations. Within this context, the principles and rule set by certain authorities on national and international platforms form the basis of conservation and restoration principles and techniques, as well as the approaches in the process of integrating ancient buildings into contemporary life.

In the restoration works examined comparatively on the theater, it is seen that interventions in the 70s caused significant changes in the structure with reconstructions and led to differences in the perception of the monument. However, restoration is the practice of repair and improvement with the least intervention as a subheading of the concept of conservation. In this context, it is observed that in the recent conservation and restoration works, the existing monument and visitor safety have been prioritized, great importance has been given to the original architectural structure and traces of historical usage, the traces have been preserved in terms of periodical additions by avoiding non-essential interventions, and "reversible" interventions have been made in some areas. In addition, in the theater, which serves its original purpose of construction today, events and concerts are organized in a controlled manner, with no use of sound amplifiers, no large decoration installations, and the seating capacity of 24,000 people is limited to 2,500 people. These restrictive measures prevent the ancient building from wear and tear.

Acknowledgements and Information Note

This article has been produced from the master's thesis titled "Evaluation Of "Reintegration" Interventions In The Through Examples Of Ancient Theatres In The Process Of Its Integration Into Contemporary Usage" completed in the Conservation and Restoration Department of the Faculty of Science at Istanbul Commerce University. The article complies with national and international research and publication ethics. Ethics committee approval was obtained for the photographic archive and drawings. Ethics Committee approval in the study, Ethics Committee of the Republic of Türkiye Ministry of Culture and Tourism, General Directorate of Cultural Heritage and Museums dated 13/12/2023. It was taken with decision no. E-99902397-176.99[176.99.35]-4533523.

Author Contribution and Conflict of Interest Declaration Information

All authors contributed equally to the article. There is no conflict of interest.

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